

PREDICTION OF ATTENUATED GUIDED WAVE PROPAGATION IN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Attenuation of Lamb waves, both fundamental symmetric and anti-symmetric modes, propagating through carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) was modeled using the multi-physics finite element methods (MP-FEM) and compared with experimental results. Composite plates typical of aerospace applications were used and provide actuation using integrated piezoelectric wafer active sensor (PWAS) transducers. The MP-FEM implementation was used to combine electro active sensing materials and structural composite materials. Simulation results obtained with appropriate level of Rayleigh damping are correlated with experimental measurements. Relation between viscous damping and Rayleigh damping are presented and the effects on wave attenuation due to material damping and geometry spreading are discussed. The Rayleigh damping model was used to compute the wave damping coefficient at several frequencies for S0 and A0 modes. The challenge of multi-modal guided Lamb wave propagation is discussed.

1 Introduction

Lamb waves (LW) are ultrasonic waves which propagate through plate-like structures and are employed for structural health monitoring (SHM) applications. Lamb waves features used for SHM are time-of-flight, mode conversion/generation, change in amplitude/attenuation, velocity, etc. [1]. Attenuation is often neglected in wave propagation analysis because of modeling complexities. In the case of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP), one of the main complexities involved in the propagation of guided waves is the attenuation effect. The different sources of energy dissipation in FRP are: (a) viscoelastic nature of matrix and/or fiber materials

[2]. (b) damping due to interphase [3]; (c) damping due to damage [4]. (d) visco-plastic damping [5]. (e) thermo-elastic damping [5]. Numerical modeling of guided wave propagation helps understanding the interaction between the material damage and the guided waves. The finite element method (FEM) approach is traditionally used for modeling elastic wave propagation [6, 7]. Many authors modeled LW propagation through FRP media without considering the damping effect [8, 9]. However, if material attenuation is also incorporated in the FEM model, then SHM techniques based on the change in amplitude can be understood better. For this reason, the prediction of the attenuation of LW in FRP is a critical issue and needs to be developed and known in coordination with experimental data. The damping model is implemented in many commercial software packages (eq. ABAQUS). Viscous damping is the only dissipation mechanism that is linear and thus low cost, so that the motivation for its use in models is very strong. The most common viscous damping description is the Rayleigh damping model, where a linear combination of mass and stiffness matrices is used. This Rayleigh damping is defined as [10]

$$[C] = \alpha[M] + \beta[K] \quad (1)$$

where α and β are the mass and stiffness proportionality coefficients. The mass proportional damping coefficient α introduces damping forces caused by the absolute velocities of the model and so simulates the idea of the model moving through a viscous “medium” [11]. The stiffness proportional damping coefficient β introduces damping proportional to the strain rate, which can be thought of as damping associated with the material itself [11].

In the present work, a Rayleigh damping model is used to study the damping of the guided Lamb wave in carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite laminates. We use composite plates typical of aerospace applications and provide actuation using integrated piezoelectric wafer active sensor (PWAS) transducers. The multi-physics finite element method (MP-FEM) implementation is used to combine electro active sensing materials and structural composite materials. Numerical studies show good correlation with experimental results with appropriate level of structural damping. The proportionality damping constants are shown to depend on the attenuation coefficient, group velocity, and central frequency of excitation. Thus estimated proportionality constants are used in numerical modeling to describe the material attenuation in the Lamb waves.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Material under Test and Experimental Set-up

The structure under investigation is a CFRP plate consisting of a carbon-fiber fabric reinforcement in an epoxy resin (Figure 1). The plate dimensions are $390 \times 395 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$.

Figure 1: Picture the network of piezoelectric wafer active sensor bonded on the CFRP.

The CFRP material is HexPly® M18/1/939; this is a woven carbon prepreg manufactured by Hexcel. This material is commonly used in aircraft industry. The plate plies have the orientation $[0, 45, 45, 0]_s$. The CFRP material properties given by the manufacturer are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: CFRP mechanical properties from Hexcel

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}
65 GPa	67 GPa	8.6 GPa
ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
0.09	0.09	0.3
G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
5 GPa	5 GPa	5 GPa
ρ		
1605 kg/m ³		

Twenty one PWAS transducers (Steminc SM412, 8.7 mm-diameter disks and 0.5 mm-thick) were used for Lamb wave propagation experiments. The PWAS network bonded on the CFRP plate is shown on Figure 1. We performed experimental acquisitions from 10 to 600 kHz in step of 3 kHz, using the T-PWAS as transducer, and the other PWAS transducers as receivers. The excitation signals were three-count tone burst modulated through Hanning window, having maximum amplitude of 20 Volts peak to peak. The instrumentation consisted of an HP33120A arbitrary signal generator, and a Tektronix TDS210 digital oscilloscope. A LabView™ computer program was developed to record the data from the digital oscilloscope, and to generate the raw data files.

2.2 Dispersion Curves in the CFRP Specimen

A computer code was developed [12] to predict the dispersion curves in a laminate composite using the analysis method developed by Nayfeh [13]. Figure 2 shows the analytical and experimental group velocity curve of the average of all direction propagation paths. Only two modes are present, A0 and S0 mode. The A0 mode velocity has a good match with the calculated dispersion curve. However a difference is found in the velocity of S0 mode. (The SH0 mode is not present because the PWAS do not excite and detect this guided wave type.) In order to improve the prediction of the dispersion curves, we updated the CFRP properties used in the analytical model (Table 2). Figure 3 shows a comparison between the experimental and the analytical group velocity curves after updating the CFRP properties.

The velocity of A0 mode is still well matched with the calculated dispersion curve. The S0 curve is now fairly good agreement with the experimental results

up to 200 kHz. Beyond 200 kHz, the experimental S0 group velocity seems to decrease more rapidly than the analytical prediction. This aspect may be due to the behavior of woven fabric laminates at high frequency which may become substantially different from the simplified assumptions of the analytical model.

Figure 2: Experimental group velocity curve compared with the theoretical predictions using the mechanical properties from the manufacturer.

Table 2: CFRP mechanical properties updating

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}
37 GPa	39 GPa	10 GPa
ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
0.1	0.1	0.3
G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
5 GPa	5 GPa	5 GPa
ρ		
1605 kg/m ³		

Figure 3: Group velocity comparison after updating the material properties in the analytical model.

It is apparent from this comparison that the material properties are very important on the accuracy of the group velocity prediction. It is also important on the magnitude of the guided Lamb waves. It is very important to know well the material properties in order to develop a SHM system for composite materials.

2.3 Tuned Guided Waves in the CFRP Specimen

Tuning of guided wave propagation in a specimen is beneficial for increasing the experimental accuracy and reducing the experimental error because it increases the signal strength. The tuning between PWAS transducers and guided waves in isotropic metallic plates is relatively well understood and modeled [1]. The gist of the concept is that manipulation of PWAS size and frequency allows the selective preferential excitation of certain guided wave modes and the rejection of other guided wave modes, as needed by the particular SHM application. A similar tuning effect is also possible in anisotropic composite plates [14, 15], only that the analysis is more complicated due to the anisotropic wave propagation characteristics inherent in composite materials and also due to the Rayleigh damping effect which propagation depends on frequency and the direction.

Figure 4: PWAS tuning guided wave in composite for the S0 mode.

Experiments on a CFRP with a PWAS transmitter and several PWAS receivers installed along various directions with respect to the fiber orientation. A three-count tone-burst modulated through a Hanning window, with frequency varying from 10 to 600 kHz in steps of 3 kHz, was used to excite the PWAS transmitter. At each frequency, the wave amplitude of the two guided wave modes: S0, and A0 was

collected. Tuning was observed when the amplitude of a certain mode peaked at a certain frequency. Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the PWAS tuning guided wave for S0 and A0 mode taking place at separate frequencies. The S0 mode reaches a peak around 300 kHz with a magnitude of 0.18 V and then decreases. The A0 reaches a peak around 90 kHz with a magnitude of 0.03 V and then decreases.

Figure 5: PWAS tuning guided wave in composite for the A0 mode.

2.4 Multi-physics Finite Element Method

The use of MP-FEM approach allows us to model the direct application of the excitation voltage at the T-PWAS and directly recording of the signal captured at the R-PWAS. The commercial software used in the present study, ABAQUS, is based on a central difference method using the implicit solver in time domain [11]. In preliminary studies [16, 17], we investigated how the group velocities of the S0 and A0 waves vary with mesh density $N = \lambda/L$, where λ is the wavelength and L is the size of the element for an isotropic structure and developed guidelines for accurate modeling of wave propagation. Following these guidelines the plate was discretized with S4R shell elements of size 1-mm in the xy plane ($N = 23$ and $N = 8$ elements per wavelength). Eight plies are used in the S4R element with the same orientation as the experimental plate described in Section 2.1. The PWAS transducers were discretized with the C3D8E piezoelectric element and assumed perfectly bonded to the plate at the locations shown on Figure 1. The piezoelectric material properties were assigned to the PWAS as described in [18]. The CFRP mechanical properties in the MP-FEM model are presented in Table 2.

Thus, we modeled the electric signal recorded at the R-PWAS due to an electric excitation applied to the T-PWAS which generated ultrasonic guided waves travelling through the plate.

3 Guided Wave Attenuation due to Material Damping for 2-D Propagation

Lamb waves can have 1-D propagation (straight-crested Lamb waves) or 2-D propagation (circular-crested Lamb waves). Conventional ultrasonic transducers generate straight-crested Lamb waves. This is usually done through an oblique impingement of the plate with a tone-burst through a coupling wedge. Circular-crested Lamb waves are not easily excited with conventional transducers. However, circular-crested Lamb waves can be easily excited with PWAS transducers, which have omnidirectional effects and generate circular-crested Lamb waves propagating in a circular pattern. Circular-crested Lamb waves have the same characteristic equation and the same across the thickness Lamb modes as the straight-crested Lamb waves. The main difference between straight-crested and circular-crested Lamb waves lies in their space-wise dependence, which is a trough harmonic function in the first case and through Bessel functions in the second case. In spite of this difference, the Rayleigh-Lamb frequency equation, which was developed for straight-crested Lamb waves, also applies to the circular-crested Lamb waves. Hence, the wave speed and group velocity of circular-crested are the same of straight-crested Lamb waves.

Figure 6 shows a prediction of circular-crested Lamb waves in a plate generated by a PWAS bonded on a composite plate. This snapshot is obtained using the MP-FEM simulation described in section 2.4. The attenuation of Lamb wave may be due to many different factors; the four most important ones are [19]: (a) Geometric spreading of the circular wave front; (b) Material damping due to internal energy dissipation; (c) Wave dispersion; (d) Dissipation into adjacent media for plates submerged in liquid. The attenuation due to **wave dispersion** is a result of a frequency dependence of wave velocities. As a particular wave packet is composed of different frequencies, these frequency components travel differently in time leading to a dispersion of the wave packet and lowering the apparent amplitude of

the wave packet. The **geometric spreading** describes the loss of amplitude due to the growing length of a wave front spreading out into all directions as illustrated in the MP-FEM simulation of Figure 6.

Figure 6: Simulation of circular crested plate wave propagation in a plate.

Figure 7 shows how the signal received at different distances from the source decreases in amplitude due to geometric spreading. The effect of the geometric spreading is a magnitude attenuation with distance which may be confused with “damping”.

Figure 7: 2D MP-FEM damping-less simulation: S0 signal received at different distance from the source displays the effect of the geometric spreading attenuation only.

The combined effect of geometric spreading and material damping can be modeled as follows. In the case of single-frequency wave propagation in a

circular wave-front through a plate with material damping, we can write [20]

$$\phi(r,t) = A \frac{1}{\sqrt{r}} e^{-\eta r} e^{i(\omega t - \gamma r)} \quad (2)$$

where r is the distance between the T-PWAS and the R-PWAS, A is the magnitude of the signal. Eq. (2) indicates that the decrease in wave amplitude with propagation (i.e. wave attenuation) consist of two components, one due to geometric spreading, $1/\sqrt{r}$, and the other due to structural damping, $e^{-\eta r}$. Plotting the magnitude of the signal received as shown on Figure 7 versus the distance, we can curve fit Eq. (2) these values. Figure 8 shows such curve fitting using the magnitude of the un-damped MP-FEM signal versus distance.

Figure 8: Curve fitting of the MP-FEM results without damping. In this case the attenuation is only due to the geometric spreading and with curve fitting with $(A = 0.5259; \eta = 0)$.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Simulation of Rayleigh Damping Coefficients Effects using MP-FEM Software

This section will present the effect of using the mass or the stiffness proportional coefficients on the received signal

The MP-FEM received signal at different distance from the source with $\alpha = 0; \beta = 5 \times 10^{-8}$ was simulated. Figure 9 shows the variation of

magnitude of the damped MP-FEM signal received versus the distance.

Figure 9: 2D MP-FEM simulation curve fitting of the peak to peak magnitude versus the received distance signal when the damping ratio is 5% ($\alpha = 0; \beta = 5 \times 10^{-8}$) and curve fitting with ($A = 0.4; \eta = 15$).

The MP-FEM signal received at different distance from the source with $\alpha = 120000; \beta = 0$ was simulated. Figure 10 shows the variation of magnitude of the damped MP-FEM signal received versus the distance.

Figure 10: 2D MP-FEM simulation curve fitting of the peak to peak magnitude versus the received distance signal when the damping ratio is 5% ($\alpha = 120000; \beta = 0$) and with curve fitting with ($A = 0.47; \eta = 15$).

As shown on Figure 9 and Figure 10, the curve of the **geometry spreading**, i.e. $1/\sqrt{r}$, and the other due to **structural damping**, i.e. $e^{-\eta r}$, fit very well the simulated data when the wave damping coefficient, $\eta = 15$.

This is very interesting because we can obtain the same simulated results using the stiffness proportional damping, or the mass proportional damping.

4.2 Estimation of Rayleigh Damping Coefficients for Multi-modal Guided Waves

The essential parameter required to estimate the Lamb wave attenuation due to material damping is the wave damping coefficient, η . The determination of η is straight forward in straight-crested guided waves because the wave attenuation can be easily traced to an exponential decay $e^{-\eta r}$. However, the generation of 1-D guided Lamb waves in physical experiments is very difficult and quite impractical. Much easier is the generation of guided waves from a “point” source, much as a small PWAS transducer. But, in this case, the guided waves front is not straight but circular. As already discuss, a circular wave front attenuated due to a combination of at least two confounding effects: (a) geometric spreading; and (b) material damping. Although our focus is interest is to determine the material damping, this cannot be done alone and the concurrent effect of geometric spreading must be also considered as illustrated in Eq. (2). Another associated difficulty is the multi-modal character of the Lamb waves where S0 and A0 modes coexist simultaneously. This latter aspect may be mitigated by exploiting the PWAS mode tuning properties [14]. In order to address this, we developed a methodology for extracting a value for the damping coefficient η from experimental 2-D propagation guided wave signals using a curve-fitting approach. In our previous work [20], we showed that the magnitude of the S0 mode tuned at 300 kHz decreases as the law described in Eq. (2) which combines geometry spreading, $1/\sqrt{r}$, with the structural damping, $e^{-\eta r}$; a good fit to the experimental data was obtained for $\eta = 15$.

However, we were surprised by the anomalous behavior of the A0 mode tuned at 90 kHz, which did not seem to follow the law described by Eq. (2) [20]. This was maybe due to the dispersion effects that modifies the wave amplitude. Ideally, Eq. (2) should apply to a single frequency excitation, but this is impractical in experiments using the tone burst excitation and wave packets.

To compare and understand the effect of geometric spreading and material damping on combined S0 and A0 modes, a study was also performed at the excitation frequency of 150 kHz when both S0 and A0 modes are present. In our previous work [21], we showed that the experimental attenuation curve fitting for S0 mode follows the curve with combined geometry spreading and the structural damping with a wave damping coefficient of $\eta = 6$. Moreover, this wave damping coefficient was in good agreement with our MP-FEM results [21]. We also showed that the attenuation of the A0 wave magnitude seems to follow the structural damping model while ignoring the geometric spreading, i.e., different from Eq. (2) [21]. We were surprised by this contradictory result, especially since the S0 mode tuned at 300 kHz did follow Eq. (2) quite well. This anomalous behavior of the A0 mode may be due to the dispersion effects that modifies the wave amplitude.

Ideally, Eq. (2) should apply to a single frequency excitation, but this impractical in experiments using the tone burst excitation and wave packages. Dispersion induced attenuation is hard to observe and has been little studied; one alternative would be to perform the study in terms of wave packet total energy instead of maximum wave amplitude. The wave packet energy can be expressed as

$$E \propto \int_{t_0}^{t_1} |x(t)|^2 dt \quad (3)$$

Where, $x(t)$ is the time signal received by the T-PWAS, t_0 and t_1 are the time window where the wave packet of interest is.

Figure 11 shows the attenuation curve fitting using the energy of the S0 mode wave packet which follows the curve with combined geometry spreading and the structural damping with a wave damping coefficient $\eta = 18.138$.

Figure 12 shows the damping curve fitting for A0 mode which follows the curve with combined

geometry spreading and the structural damping only structural damping, with a wave damping coefficient $\eta = 16.008$.

Figure 11: Experimental curve fitting at different distance at 150 kHz for the S0 mode with ($A = 0.5638$; $\eta = 18.138$) using wave energy.

Figure 12: Experimental curve fitting at different distance at 150 kHz for the A0 mode with ($A = 0.3645$; $\eta = 16.008$).

Knowing the wave damping coefficient η and the group velocity for a given frequency, we can plot the mass proportional damping α versus the stiffness proportional damping β using the equation:

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha + \beta\omega^2) = \eta c_0 \quad (4)$$

The difficulty appears when the guided wave propagation is multi-modal, i.e. at 150 kHz. Figure 13 shows the α - β curves at 150 kHz for S0 and A0 mode. It is apparent that the α - β curves do not intersect, i.e. we cannot find a common combination of α and β that simultaneously satisfies the A0 and S0 modes.

Figure 13: Model of α versus β (Rayleigh damping coefficients) for the CFRP laminate at 150 kHz for S0 and A0 mode.

4.3 Simulation of the Guided Wave Propagation with Rayleigh damping for multi-modal Lamb waves

The MP-FEM simulation was carried out on a CFRP laminate described in the section 2.6 to determine the attenuation coefficient. A 150 kHz three-tone burst modulated by a Hanning window with a 20 Volts maximum amplitude peak to peak was applied to the top surface of the T-PWAS. Due to the dispersion curves presented in section 2.2 and the tuning effect described on section 2.3, both S0 and A0 modes are present at this frequency.

Figure 14 shows the comparison between the MP-FEM simulation and the experimental signal measured at R-PWAS placed at 100 mm from the T-PWAS. A Rayleigh damping was used; the stiffness proportional coefficient $\beta = 6.10^{-8}$ corresponds to the S0 mode attenuation shown in Figure 13.

Figure 14 shows that the excitation frequency of 150 kHz, two guided wave modes are present, S0 and A0. The A0 mode is considerably slower than the S0 mode and its magnitude is smaller than the S0 magnitude; this agrees with the tuning curve in section 2.5. However, for this stiffness proportional coefficient $\beta = 6.10^{-8}$, the MP-FEM magnitude for

the A0 mode is smaller than the experiment value, i.e. the damping coefficient is too big to simulate the experimental results.

Figure 14: Comparison between the experimental and the MP-FEM received signal at 100 mm from the T-PWAS at 150 kHz with $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 6.10^{-8}$.

Figure 15 shows the comparison between the MP-FEM simulation and experimental electric signal measured at R-PWAS placed at 100 mm from the T-PWAS with the stiffness proportional coefficient $\beta = 2.10^{-8}$ which corresponds to the A0 mode attenuation shown in Figure 13. With this stiffness proportional coefficient $\beta = 2.10^{-8}$, the MP-FEM signal for the S0 and the A0 modes are in better agreement with the experimental signal.

Figure 15: Comparison between the experimental and the MP-FEM received signal at 100 mm from the T-PWAS at 150 kHz with $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 2.10^{-8}$.

However, the MP-FEM signal between the S0 mode packet and the A0 mode packet is different from the experimental signal. This different signal may be due to the scattering effect by the other bonded PWAS on the guided wave propagation path between the T-PWAS and the R-PWAS as described on the MP-FEM snapshot on Figure 16.

Figure 16: Snapshot of the guided Lamb wave propagation showing the scattering due to the bonded PWAS on the guided wave propagation path between the T-PWAS and the R-PWAS.

In addition, we may attribute these phenomena to a micro defect that we observed in the structure as shown on the scanning acoustic microscopy picture on Figure 17 and Figure 18.

Figure 17: Scanning acoustic microscopy of the first layer at 0/90 degree.

Indeed, on the first layer (0/90 degree) and on the second layer (45/-45 degree), we observe some area of resin pocket and lake of resin, respectively. These micro defects can create some scattering effect

and/or conversion mode on the guided wave which is observed on the received signal on Figure 15.

Figure 18: Scanning acoustic microscopy of the first layer at 45/-45 degree.

5 Conclusion

This paper has presented numerical and experimental results on the use of guided wave for structural health monitoring (SHM) in viscoelastic composite material. Guided wave simulation was conducted with the multi-physics finite element method (MP-FEM) in a multi-layer composite material. The simulated electrical signal was excited at a T-PWAS and measured at a R-PWAS using the MP-FEM capability.

Relation between viscous damping and Rayleigh damping were presented and a discussion was done about wave attenuation due to material damping and geometry spreading. It was found that the mass or stiffness proportional damping coefficients have the same effect on the attenuation of guided waves for the S0 mode. The Rayleigh damping model was used to compute the wave damping coefficient for S0 and A0 mode. The multi-modal guided wave propagation was also examined by excitation at 150 kHz where both the A0 and S0 modes are present. We found that the reduction in energy for S0 and A0 modes packet obey a law that incorporates both geometry spreading and structural damping. It was found that the mass and/or stiffness proportional damping coefficient are different for each mode. Nonetheless, using these coefficients, we were able

to simulate these two modes using our MP-FEM approach with high accuracy.

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